

THE USE OF SEGMENTS OF FREQUENCY IN THE NAMES OF MEDICINES IN THE PHARMACEUTICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract. This article presents the most frequently used segments and their values using examples that make it possible to differentiate a drug or medicinal product by therapeutic, anatomical or physiological nature. Segments of frequency are the verbal segments that have specific meanings and contains some information about the chemical composition of a drug. The purpose of using segments of frequency is to systematize medicines according to their effect on the body, as well as to form indications for their use.

Keywords: segments of frequency, pharmaceutical terminology, common names, systematization, chemical composition.

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СЕГМЕНТОВ ЧАСТОТЫ В НАИМЕНОВАНИЯХ ЛЕКАРСТВ В ФАРМАЦЕВТИЧЕСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. В статье представлены наиболее часто используемые сегменты и их значения на примерах, которые позволяют дифференцировать лекарственное средство или медицинский продукт по терапевтической, анатомической или физиологической природе. Сегменты частоты — это глагольные сегменты, имеющие определенное значение и содержащие некоторую информацию о химическом составе препарата. Целью использования сегментов частоты является систематизация лекарственных средств по их воздействию на организм, а также формирование показаний к их применению.

Ключевые слова: сегменты частоты, фармацевтическая терминология, общепринятые названия, систематизация, химический состав.

Introduction

Medical students of the 1st course study Latin and medical terminology. Latin, which is considered the language of medicine, is used in medicine in anatomical, clinical and pharmaceutical terminology. Specialists working in the pharmaceutical industry, regardless of their position, use pharmaceutical terminology. Pharmaceutical terminology is a set of terms related to a corresponding system of concepts. The terminological system corresponds to the level of modern development of the pharmaceutical industry. Many basic pharmaceutical terms are borrowed from Greek and Latin. The fundamentals of pharmaceutical terminology were briefly formulated by the Russian scientist M.N.Chernavsky [30].

In his textbook on Latin, the author outlined the characteristics of the concept and functions of the term, provided information on definitions, terminology, types of terminological systems in the field of pharmacy, on the basic pharmaceutical nomenclatures and principles of the formation of a term or nomenclature based on classical languages.

Materials and methods: In pharmaceutical terminology, segments of frequency are distinguished that divide medicines into groups according to their medicinal properties, and also allow us to classify many medicines and navigate a large number of medicines. The word-forming elements that retain their semantic meaning in the names of medicines are called pharmaceutical frequency segments or terminological elements. A segment of frequency is a segment that has a certain value and contains some information about the chemical composition of a drug and its effectiveness with a therapeutic effect. In Latin, there are many segments of frequency that make it possible to differentiate a medicine or medicine by therapeutic, anatomical, or physiological nature. A segment of frequency is a verbal segment that has a certain meaning and contains some information about the chemical composition of a drug and its effectiveness with a therapeutic effect. Latin has many segments of frequency that make it possible to differentiate a drug or medicinal product by therapeutic, anatomical, or physiological nature. Knowing the frequency intervals will help you spell many complex pharmaceutical terms correctly, as well as understand the general meaning of these terms.

The purpose of using segments of frequency was to systematize medicines according to their effect on the body, as well as to form indications for their use. With their help, many medicines can be easily put into practice, regardless of their chemical structure and raw materials for production. The following are examples of segments of frequency that are most common in pharmaceutical practice. For example, the segments of frequency *-alg-*, *-dol-*, denoting pain, is used when naming painkillers: **Analginum**, **Baralginum**, **Promedolum**; the segment of frequency with the value *-vit-* denotes multivitamin complexes: **Aevitum**, **Complivitum**, **Picovitum**, **Revitum**; segment of frequency *-cid-* antimicrobial action: **Streptocidum**; *-cor-*, *-card-* cardiotonic, cardiac: **Corvalolum**, **Cardiomagnil**, **Stenocard**; *-vas-*, *-angi-* antispasmodic, vasodilating: **Vasocor**, **Divascolum**, **Angitolum**; *-press-*, *-tens-* tonic, hypotensive: **Apressinum**, **Depressan**, **Protensinum**, **Tensidomin**; *-nas-*, *-rhin-* for the treatment of nasal diseases: **Nasivin**, **Rhinoxil**, **Nasonex**, **Rhinza**; *-oc-*, *-ok-*, *-ocu-*, *-ophthalm-*, *-oft-*, *-opt(ic)-* for the treatment of eye diseases: **Octilia**, **Okacin**, **Ocupress**, **Digophthon**, **Oftensin**, **Optimol**, **Betoptic**; *-spasm-* treatment of spasms, convulsive muscle contractions: **Spasmalgon**, **Spasmol**, **Spasmex**; *-aller-*, *-anth-(flower)*, *-phyll-(leaf)* anti-allergic: **Allergolum**, **Allergodil**, **Strophanthinum**, **Platyphyllinum**; *-somm-*, *-barb-*, *-dorm-*, *-hypn-*, *-mal-*, *-al* sleeping pills: **Barbamylum**, **Corbamalum**, **Somnafinum**, **Dormital**; *-fem-*, *-gyn-* for the treatment of gynecological diseases:

Femoden, Femara, Gynalgin; -cut(i)-, -derm- for the treatment of skin diseases: **Dermasol, Dermovate, Dermoclinum, Prododerm, Dermotonal; -bil-, -chol- (col)** choleric: **Bilergenum, Cholaminum, Etacolum, Cholevinum, Allochol, Febichol; -aesthes-** anesthetic, painkiller: **Anaesthesinum, Aesthesifinum; -haemat-, -aemia-** the relative of blood: **Haematogenum; -lax-** laxative: **Acetolax, Picolax, Laxasept, Laxatin; -pyr-** antipyretic: **Amidopyrinum; -sed-** sedative: **Sedeval, Sedonic, Sedavitum; -stress-, -tranqu-** antidepressant drugs: **Anastress, Tranquil, Stressovitum; -thromb-** anticoagulant agent: **Antithrombinum; -ur-** diuretic: **Diurometan, Saurinum; Urolesan, Urotol, Uracton; -verm-, -helm (int)** anthelmintic: **Univerm, Helminthinum, Vermox, Vermazol, Helmadol; -vom(it)-** against vomiting: **Vomitral, Emitiral; -test-, vir-, andr-, ster-** male sex hormone preparations: **Agovirinum, Testosteronum; -myco-, -fungi-** antifungal: **Mycosolonum, Mycoseptinum, Myconasolum, Mycosoral, Myconid, Funginal; -sept-** decontaminating agents: **Enteroseptolum, Septolete, Septonasal, Septofeminum, Septilinum; -thyr-** affecting thyroid function: **Thyrotrophinum, Thyrosinum, Thyrosolum, Thyrothrycin** and so on. Segments of frequency are often understood to include terms known from the anatomical and clinical terminology course. For example: **Venitan** (lat. vena vein), **Pulmex** (lat. pulmo lungs), **Senade** (bot. lat. Senna senna), **Thymolinum** (lat. thymus the thymus gland), **Vincapanum** (lat. Vinca periwinkle, (a preparation from the alkaloids of the periwinkle plant), **Apilacum** (lat. apis bee + lac milk), **Spleninum** (gr. splen the spleen), **Ovestin** (lat. ovum ovum) and so on.

Results and discussion: Over time, deformations and changes have occurred in the pharmaceutical nomenclature in different languages, so many drugs do not have segments of frequency, they are called by a special individual name, for example, *Paracetamolum*. But segments of frequency are still present in drugs used in different languages of the world, so doctors and pharmacists can easily recognize them from fragments of drug names, even in different languages. In practical medicine, this is of great importance in the work of doctors in various fields, which makes it possible to understand the treatment system for patients who come with various pathologies.

General observations: Students are offered to memorize the most commonly used segments of frequency, from which the names of pharmaceutical drugs are compiled. To do this, we introduced segments of frequency over the course of five classes, starting with the topic "Introduction to pharmaceutical Terminology" and ending with the topic "Prescription abbreviations". Accordingly, in each of these classes, exercises were presented to consolidate these word-forming elements. 90% of the students were able to spell correctly and correctly the names of medicines with frequency intervals, while the rest found it difficult to spell the names of medicines.

Conclusion: Doctors all over the world can easily understand the meaning of treatment prescribed by their colleagues or another specialist, as well as help differentiate between “fake” medicines. This is of great importance when prescribing medications and their dosage. In addition to frequency segments, the Latin language has introduced into the pharmaceutical industry a large number of names of natural and synthetic raw materials, so that it is easy to distinguish the medicinal properties of the components and the drug itself.

Pharmaceutical companies around the world use Latin segments of frequency to refer to medicines, in addition, doctors use medicines that are already known to the medical community, which have segments of frequency in their names. This makes it easier to differentiate the drug and understand its therapeutic effect. In medicine, Latin is a universal way for doctors and pharmacists to communicate. The Latin terminology is very rich and allows the doctor to find out the diagnosis and treatment of the patient. If future pharmacists, provisors, and doctors also know these segments of frequency by heart, they can easily learn the composition or active ingredient of the drug, although there are analogues with names in different languages.

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